

**THE PERSPECTIVE STUDY OF USE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY
IN TEACHING –LEARNING PROCESS OF SECONDARY
HIGH SCHOOL LEVEL IN SHIRUR TAJBAND**

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Introduction :-

In the 21 century everybody want to need use of information technology Everybody must have to know the knowledge of computer. Every on has the Knowledge of inforamton technology to stand on the global competition. In the reason computer subject is include in the school curriculum. Teacher must be use of technology in his teaching for process and to know the information of computer Indias good prophesy hide in the rural area. Today we seen the fig. negation of information technology in use of rural area's school. Teacher cannot use information techonology in his teaching the lack of good. Facilities. In that reason deceived form that inforamton. Today every body must know about the use of information technologyin the rural area. This basic need.

**Research Theme :- The perspective study of use informaton technology in teachin –
Learning Process of secondary high school Level in Shirur
Tajband**

Need and Importance of Research :-

Indias 70% people lives in the rural area, when we begin research that time we can't Lea loose the rural area. The comparison between rural and urban students we come to know that in learning proces urban students are talented than rural students. Because of use of internet , through computer. In the city available of fundamental facilities of information technology etc.

We always says that 21st century is the competition era. Every students to live good life is most important and face competetion for that reason every student must use the information technology but rural students has not of problems in the use of information technology for this reason of tools the present short reserch paper.

Research Objectives :-

1. To know the problems of high school level students in information technology.
2. To know the use of information technoloyg by teachers.
3. To recommended the problems of learning process.
4. To recommended the problems of teaching process.

Assumption of Research :-

1. In rural area's students to not available the fundamental facilities of informaton technology.
2. The rural side teacher's have many problems to use information technology in teaching process.

Sampling :-

The present short research paper has included the village shirrur tajband in Ahmedpur Taluka at. Shirur tajband there are Two high schools. From this five teachers & Ten students from each high school has including for this short research Thus 10 teacher & 20 Students has selected purposive sampling by this sampling method.

Research Methodology :-

The present research paper express to know about the secondary schools in use of information technology by present position that's why to use the survey method for this Research.

Research Tools :

Present short Research paper express secondary level technology has edded to study that reason to determined The questionarship. Tool from questinary tools to students and teachers and gathered the whole information.

Statistical Tools :-

In the present short research paper percentage is used as statistical tools.

Scope and Limitations :-

1. The present research paper's scope has only limited of secondary school of Shirur Tajband.
2. The present Research paper have only use of inforamton technology of Shirur Tajband Secondary High School.

Actual Working :-

The present Reserch paper have fixed area of Shirur Tajband in this village two high schools are there. In these two high schools we selected five teachers and ten students to took the one question aries by made up to special objects. This questionaries fill up by students and teachers and recaptulation of both information .

To gainde the definite meaning of these problem to use percentage and statistical tools and lastly to proffed * then some regular dispositoin are recommended.

➤ Teacher Respanse Table :-

Q.No.	Question	Response No.	Percentage
1	To have special computer Room	10	100
2	In school time table included weekly two periods of computer	09	90
3	In every computer simultaniously sits three or more students	05	50
4	Some times to used computer in teaching	06	60
5	In teaching do not use Radio	10	100
6	To use news paper of educational news	08	80
7	In teaching process to use T.V. of educational program	08	80
8	Do not use of teprecorder in teaching	04	40
9	Do not use of Vido inteaching	04	40
10	Lack of elctricity in the problem in use of technological tools in teaching	09	90
11	i. Always use available of elcectricity in computer lab	10	100

	ii. Includes of English new papers.	03	30
	iii. Expert teachers guidance	04	40
12	i. One computer literary persons to selcet to give computer knowledge.	04	40
	ii. in students to spread used of knowledge	06	60
	iii. Every students to handle the computer	07	70

Students Responce Table :-

Q.No.	Question	Response No.	Percentage
1	Only math & science teacher who use computer in teaching	18	90
2	In time table weekly on period of computer subject	10	50
3	Infact every weekly to give on period	16	80
4	One time 3-4 suddents sits on one computer	10	50
5	Some times teachers uses information technology in teaching	11	55
6	Programme of radio do not hears students	17	85
7	The programme on television do not see the students	20	100
8	Only use of columns/maps in teaching process	19	95
9	The news paper reading in interval time only	19	95
10	i. The use of Computer	18	90
11	ii. Chart/maps/Models use in teaching	20	100
12	iii. The use of Radio & Tap record	15	75
13	The use of Television & Video	16	80
14	i. To use L.C.D. Projector in teaching	16	80
15	ii. To use of Computer	15	75
16	iii. The use of T.V.	14	70
17	iv. Modern lab is must available	15	75

Conclusion :-

By teachers Response

1. The opinion of 100% teacher of every school has special computer lab.
2. The opinion of 90% teachers the rule of time table every week has to provides by computers.
3. The opinion of 50% teachers by each computer on time simultaneous three & above students use sitting .
4. 60% teachers are used to computer sometimes.
5. In teaching process no any teachers not use radio.
6. The opinion of 80% teachers of the news paper used by any for educational views.
7. The opinion of 80% teachers in teaching procers the use of T.V. by understatnding students
8. 40% teachers never use tape recorder.
9. 40% teacher they were never use video for teaching process.
10. The opeinon of 90% teachers the use of educational technology the lack of good electivity is main problems of teaching process.
11. The opinion of 100% teachers in the rural areas schools computer lab has always availale electricity.
12. The opinion of 30% teachers in school reading lab include the english news papers.
13. The opinion of 40% teacher are to arrange the guidance of proper guides.
14. The opinion of 40 % teachers for guiding of good computer of selceted perfect man
15. The opinion of 70% teachers every student has handle a computer.
16. The opeinon of 60% teachers is that the students know the importance of technology and computer .

Conclusion by students Response :-

1. The opinion of 90% students only math & science teachers are used computer in teaching process.
2. The opinion 50% students in weekly only are period of computer
3. The opinion of 50% students each computer simultancously three four students.
4. The opinion of 55% students teachers used information technology some times in teaching process.
5. The opinion of 85% students have programmings of Radio not hears simultaneously.
6. The opinion of 100% students not available of Educational time table .
7. The 45% teachers use maps in teaching process.
8. The opinion of 95% Students are gives proper reading.
9. The opinion of 90% students use computer in teaching process.
10. The use of Tape recorder, Radio, T.V. Video in teaching process.
11. The use of L.C.D. etc most tools are used in teaching process.

Recommendations :-

1. Minimum newspapers are available in the school & minimum time give for reading.
2. Every Student learn to handle computer & at one time only one students sit on computer.
3. The time table for programmes an Radio & T.V. Must be give to the students.
4. Teacher must use various I.T. tools in his teaching
5. In rural area at least in computer lab must be supply of Electricity.

Reference Books :-

1. Study Material, Proficiency in Desk Top publishing, All India Council for Professional Training & Research
2. Partners in Learning Microsoft – Microsoft corporation (India) Pvt. Ltd Gurgaon , 122 002
3. Research Methodology, John Best